

SOCIAL FIGURATIONS AND TOURIST DISPLACEMENT IN ARGENTINA

Gómez ELÍAS

*National Council of Scientific and Technical Research;
National University of Misiones, Argentina*
E-mail: lsgomez001@gmail.com;

Carla COSSI

*National Council of Scientific and Technical Research;
National University of Misiones, Argentina*
E-mail: carlacossi@gmail.com;

ABSTRACT

In this paper analyze, on the one hand; the figurations of transnational tourist travels; and secondly, tourism concepts involving these configurations. We will do it, based on two initial questions: a) the exploration of the profiles movements than affecting tourism in Argentina; and b) the characterization of tourists and tourism in this country, during the period 2009-2014. To achieve our goals, we will use multidimensional statistics, and qualitative analysis of categories. We try to make an approach to the problem, showing that the displacements of people across state territories are transformations toward explicit new forms of social integration, which are also the stimulators and the centerpieces of tourism industry.

Keywords: *Tourism, Social Figurations, Argentina*

Tourism, tourists and figurations

The Tourism from an economic perspective is a set of export goods (CEPAL, 2015), and works as "... an engine of economic growth, inclusive development and environmental sustainability" (UNWTO, 2015; WB, 2015). Tourism, covers the travel and accommodation made by people in different places of their

habitual residence; the minimum amount of stay as a tourist is a day or a night and the largest stay usually are six months or one year, within this period vary the terms of each country. At national and international level, tourism-related agencies recognize differences among types of tourists, and differences between tourism and migration.

«International Visitor: any person who makes a tourist trip, regardless of whether

or not you stay in the place visited. International tourist: every visitor who spends at least one night in the place visited (takes a trip with overnight). International hiker or visitor of the day: the one visitor who does not spend the night in the place visited (makes a tour or visit a day). Touristic Trip: any journey with less than one year that targets a location outside the normal home environment as long as there is not visited on a weekly basis. Displacements whose main reason the performance of an activity under a wage employment relationship are excluded, or where the transfer is part of the job. (AET, 2013: 266)».

Globally, countries with the highest number of international tourist arrivals should most of the same, to arrivals from countries of the same region or subregion (Europe, North America, Asia and the Pacific). This is because tourism from an anthropological perspective is a «total social fact» linked mainly to political, cultural and economic agreements between countries. At the present, countries not only allow the interference of transnational agencies in their territories, but begin to join in supranational political communities like the European Union, or Unasur beginning to take its first steps and which Argentina is a member. Mercosur, as a sub-regional bloc aimed to facilitating the association of the economies of member countries (Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay and Uruguay, Venezuela and Uruguay) advances in this direction, and has great impact on the economy and tourism in Argentina. Thus, the displacements of tourists between member countries and associate countries of Mercosur (Chile, Bolivia [since 2015], Colombia, and Peru) demand minimal requirements, being sufficient legal proof of identity (national identity card, identity card, passport, etc.). Then, Tourism urges States to establish relations of cooperation and joint planning,

and encourages the formation of larger supranational units. Figurations of tourist travel, such as networks of political and economic interdependencies, promotes the emergence of populations less tied to the old organizational structures of States. As Elias notes (1982), changes in identification of people with ever larger organizational units, are not exempt from suffering experienced as deeply individual.

So, identities and feelings of belonging change dramatically when people stop being loyal to smaller clans to feel part of large tribes, tribal societies, cities, empires, states and supranational communities at the present. In this sense, the tourists are part of «global generations» (Beck, 2008) driven to compare and appropriate natures, cultures, politics, and economies that cannot longer be enclosed by state societies. The dynamic density of modern societies are not absolutely dependent on resident populations in defined territories by States, but also large «floating population» (Beck, 1998; Krautstoft, 2014) that after settle down a short period of time, leave the visited territories.

The global displacements of people is recurrent in various parts of the world, as shown by Wallerstein (1979, 2010) and Wolf (1993, 1999) and is not even an absolute attribute of capitalism. Although migrations as violent expulsions of States weakened by unregulated production systems are eminently current (Sassen, 2014; Villalón, 1999; Taran, 2009). For Mauss «You would say that social life causes the body and individual consciousness a violence that cannot be endured for a long time and that's why the individual is forced to reduce their social life or escape it in part.» (1979: 428). So, displacements are not limited to the social life of human populations, but the entire social life. And tourist travel are just one of the possible forms of social displacements. Thus, displacements are not limited to the social

Figure 1: *N-gram based on the frequency of occurrence of the terms “tourism”, “tourist”, “ecotourism” and “sightseeing” in books written in English, indexed by Google Books and published from 1800 to 2008. Source: n-gram-Viewer (2015).*

life of human populations, but the entire social life. And tourist travel are just one of the possible forms of social displacements.

The tourist is a relatively new type of traveler as massive figure, that is liable to be found anywhere in the world. The tourist, as subject of tourist travel, is a social production more strongly associated with recent global capitalism (Adler, 1989). The «tourist» respecter comes from «tour», and is often associated with the «turns» that the English upper middle class performed from the mid-sixteenth century until approximately the eighteenth century to European countries like Italy, France, and others. While «tourism» and «sightseein (as seen in Figure 1), emerging with force, newly between the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, as linked to, companies massively organized. And ecotourism and tourism in natural spaces emerge newly in the 90s.

Tourism presupposes the production of means of transport, cheap and mass to reorganize spaces, and the creation of working days and holidays, to reorganize the times. The “democratization of leisure” globally, less than a century (Pastoriza, 2015), that is, the establishment of the holidays, it allowed people to legally have

a period of time away from their duties. Even today-and in spite of the flexibility of labor agreements for each individual sphere of activity, country and region- the holiday seasons of the issuing countries are an important factor of variation, while the economies of the countries receivers strive to attract tourists all year round.

The causes of the election of certain destinations by tourists are dissimilar but their frameworks can be delineated from an anthropological perspective. Thus, a common feature is the world’s recognition of certain cultural traditions, economic, or political. This is evidenced by the annual and global rankings over the last decade, which put Spain, United States, France, China, UK, Italy, and Turkey as countries with the largest number of arrivals (UNWTO, 2015). The main common feature of these countries is that visitors from all over the world can appreciate in advance and proximity the peculiarities of these destinies -thanks to cinema, literature, media, among others- without actually being immersed in the world social of those places. The recognition of certain places as pleasant is even before the ‘competition between destinations’ (Tamar, 2008: 7) that is,

transnational struggles between states, regions and corporations for production and consolidation of tourist destinations.

The tourist as the foreign which analyzes Simmel (1908), can get close to others as if they were equal to himself, without actually sharing the social constraints acting on the others. This is a closed possibility, for people that form a permanent part of the everyday lives of those places. In this sense, there is “... a perfectly positive relationship” (Simmel, 1908: 2011), which allows tourists, safely experiment on himself, the social relationships that are not in doubt in its place of origin. Then, from an anthropological perspective, a tourist is a person traveling to distant places of your home, in order to experience changes (Stronza, 2001; Smith 1989); this experience of changes serves to the tourist, to return transformed to their place of origin, not to settle permanently in the tourist destination. In the case of ecotourism there is also a positive gain or symbolic relationship, because travelers pursue natures, no longer recognized as such in the everyday life of their hometowns.

The friendly and tourist natures consist of mountains, rivers, waterfalls, palm trees, forests, etc., not risky natures made of trash, cockroaches, seeds, fuels and smog. In Western culture, nature is continually opposed to the social life so it is difficult for people to recognize cohabiting same place (Latour, 2004; Thevenot, 2006). And a usual way of dealing social issues since distance, is go to nature as a symbolic north, that is to say, as a place where prevail totally opposite rules to social rules (no doubt this place is imaginary). Thus tourist companies produce natural environments that actually serve as laboratories for the social reflexivity of tourists. Finally, most of tourism in South America is eco-tourism, as the tourism in Argentina.

International tourist displacement in Argentina (2009-2014)

We say “international tourist displacement” to mean tourist arrivals to Argentina from foreign countries, and the departures of resident tourists in Argentina to

Figure 2: Cluster of international tourist arrivals (2009-2014). In green arrivals “non-regional”, in blue arrivals “Brazil”, in scarlet arrivals provenance “Boundary and Other”. Prepared based SIET (2014).

Figure 3: Cluster of international tourist arrivals (2009-2014). In green arrivals “non-regional”, in blue arrivals “Brazil”, in scarlet arrivals provenance “Boundary and Other”. Prepared based SIET (2014).

foreign destinations. The country’s position in regard to regional and global tourism, shows the main features in the way they acquire displacement configurations. But look for the defining of displacement in the annual or monthly frequency of each provenance does not simplify the complexity of the figurations. The analysis of the morphology seasonal-understood by Mauss- of tourism in Argentina, requires focus on the regular processes of tourist displacement, rather than the absolute amounts of displacement of years, months or decades.

The arrivals of Argentina since 2009 to 2014, have top quarters (first and fourth), and retiring quarters (second and third). Among other factors, these variations are due fundamentally to the formal delimitation of the holiday periods in the countries of tourists; and partly due to the predominant type of tourism in Argentina (ecotourism is highly dependent

on environmental factors such as weather, seasons, etc.). So that, international tourist arrivals predominant in Argentina are strongly associated with the summer; and retraction of arrivals with the autumn, winter and spring (as seen in Figure 2). The Ascending hierarchical classification. (see annex) of the quarterly arrivals since the years 2009 to 2014 (Figure 3) allows us to differentiate initially, arrivals predominantly regional (Brazil, Uruguay, rest of America, Brazil and Paraguay) of the predominantly non-regional arrivals (Chile, United States/Canada, Europe, and Rest of World) according to frequency similarities in all quarters.¹

Then, on the dotted horizontal line of the tree, we can differentiate in more detail, three new types of tourist arrivals. So we have a group of arrivals mostly from sources “Bordering and Other” formed by Uruguay, rest of America,

¹ Countries and groups of countries used in the analysis, correspond to those used by AET (2015).

Figure 4: Cluster of international tourist departures (2009-2014). In Blue group of departures to “Europe”, in pink departures to provenances “non-regional”, and purple departures to “Boundary and Other”. Prepared based SIET (2014).

Bolivia, and Paraguay; a group arrivals of “Brazil”; and a group arrivals of “non-regional” composed by Chile, United States/Canada, Europe, and Rest of World (as shown in Figure 4). The arrivals of “Bordering and Other” relate more to arrivals from countries of the region and shows how growing continuously since 2009 (Figure 3) but, are not limited to global seasonal cycles, that affect the rest of the international arrivals; this feature is very convenient for tourism in Argentina, because it evades the cultural ecological constraints for seasonal variations, providing economic inputs held throughout the year. The arrivals group of “Brazil” has the largest number of international arrivals as a single country; Arrivals from this country do not follow a stable pattern since 2009 to 2014; as if they were more related to dynamic factors such as foreign exchange, rather than to structural social factors. The “non-regional” arrivals (Chile, United States/Canada, Europe, and Rest of the

world) for its part, encompasses tourist arrivals from other regions of the world (except Chile); a peculiar feature of these types of arrivals that have seasonal variations and very marked cycles, unlike the other groups of arrivals.

Moreover, tourist departures of persons resident in Argentina, shows some differences and similarities with the arrivals of non-resident tourists in the country. Since 2009 to 2014 the tourist departures from the country (37.479.008) were higher than arrivals (32.084.747). There is a clear superiority of the Departures from Argentina in the first quarter and in summer, on the departures in other quarters and seasons. This trend is more marked than the seasonal variations in international tourist arrivals, although agree to the predominance of the first quarter and in the summer season (Figure 5). The retraction periods of departures, are also more pronounced, that retraction periods arrivals, although involving the same quarters (second and third).

Figure 5: Cluster departures according quarters (2009-2014). Prepared based SIET (2014).

By analyzing clustering of quarterly data since 2009 through 2014, we can distinguish two groups at the beginning (Figure 6). One consists of departures to destinations No Regional (Europe and United States/ Canada, Bolivia, Rest of the World) and another by mostly regional Departures (Uruguay, Brazil, Chile, Paraguay and elsewhere). Disaggregating more, groups of international departures. The “Non-regional” departures (Bolivia, United States / Canada, Rest of America) not follow cycles marked though, the annual record are in the first and third quarters. Departures of “Bordering and Others” (Brazil, Chile, Uruguay, Uruguay, Rest of the World) are the majority in all quarters and years, and their seasonal variations are strongly marked by records in the first quarters. The Departures to “Europe” (Europe) does not seem to follow cycles, but since 2013 begin to oscillate between top in the third and second quarters.

Conclusions

To conclude, we will return to some ideas above outlined. We remember that in “TOURISM, TOURISTS AND FIGURATIONS” we have presented the peculiarities of tourism and tourist trips to historical, global and regional level; later in INTERNATIONAL TOURIST TRAVEL IN ARGENTINA, we analyze processes and regularities, which take the arrivals and departures of international tourists in the country. Thus, as of here, we synthesize the implications of the analysis of tourist travel, trying to redefine the notion of tourism implied in our region. One of the initial interrogations of this paper it was: what are the profiles of displacements affecting the tourism in Argentina?. The analysis of tourism requires the analysis of the movement of people, things, and ideas. The movement of tourists schemes are then, the first step of a regional analysis

of tourism, to which must be added, the procesual analysis of currency exchange, and cultural and policies measures adopted by countries and regions.

As Sayad (2010) concerning migrations we analyze the international arrivals and departures as part of the same process. Tourist arrivals and departures are the two poles of the figurations of tourist travel. The concept of figuration, linking two or more tips of the procedural relations of interdependence among the various actors (in this case countries and regions of the world). This double movement reveals a central property of tourist travel, such as displacements cultural, economic and political predominantly *lived*, to destinations for cultural, economic, and political displacement predominantly *imagined*. This is also, the answer to the second initial question about how figurations affecting tourist travel in the characterization of tourism in Argentina.

In summary, the greatest contribution of tourist arrivals, come from Brazil. And mostly of tourist outings from Argentina, goes towards "Boundary and Others countries" (Brazil, Chile, Paraguay, Uruguay, Rest of World). The arrivals from Brazil, are sufficiently peculiar as to form a single group, also predominant; and into the tourist arrivals and departures,

it is the only group consisting of a single country. The Departures of tourists from Argentina, are more cyclical than tourist arrivals, although both peaks are mostly in the first quarter. The arrivals and departures to the neighboring countries, and the arrivals and departures from the neighboring countries are the majority. So, the tourism in Argentina is mostly regional tourism (linked to neighboring countries and members of Mercosur) and highly emissive. While some go out, others come to Argentina, this leads us to think tourist travel primarily as social displacements. That is, no matter how accurate and extensive are the data of tourists? They do not know the places like residents who are immersed in these cultural, economic and political conditions. The capacity of enjoyment and recreation is not inherent to tourist destinations in themselves, but into the imaginary biases of the tourists and residents. These disparities around the ways to appreciate a country or a destination are reconcilable, and help to shape supranational or regional identities. Since the configurations of interdependences between countries, tourists and residents, places of departure and destination, are not just external relations, but, a fundamental part of the social structure of supranational identities.

REFERENCES

- Sayad Abdelmalek. 2010. *La doble ausencia. De las ilusiones del emigrado a los padecimientos del inmigrado*. Barcelona, Anthropos.
- Beck Ulrich (1998): *¿Qué es la globalización? Falacias del globalismo, respuestas a la globalización*. Barcelona, Buenos Aires, México D.F. Paidós.
- Krautstoff Elena, 2014. «Territorio de fronteras y espacio de cuerpo y mujer. Peregrinación transnacional de las paseras entre Posadas (Argentina) y Encarnación (Paraguay)». *La Rivada* 3: 1-16
- Pastoriza Elisa. 2015. «El turismo social en la Argentina durante el primer peronismo. Mar del Plata, la conquista de las vacaciones y los nuevos rituales obreros, 1943-1955». *Nuevo Mundo Mundos Nuevos*. [En ligne], Débats, mis en ligne le 16 juin 2008, consulté le 29 juillet 2015; URL: <http://nuevomundo.revues.org/36472>.
- Simmel George. 2012. *El Extranjero*.

- Barcelona: SEQUITUR.
- Smith Valene(ed.).1989. *Hosts and Guests: The Anthropology of Tourism*. Philadelphia: Univ. Penn. Press. 2nd ed.
- Tamar Diana Wilson. 2008. «The Impacts of Tourism in Latin America». *Latin American Perspectives*.35: 3–20.
- TaranPatrick. 2009. «Globalización, derechos humanos y migraciones: desafíos para el desarrollo y la cohesión social.»EnPablo Ceriani Cernadas y Pablo Finkelstein (ed.) *Políticas migratorias y derechos humanos*. Buenos Aires, Universidad nacional de Lanús.
- Villalón Adriana. 1999. «Políticas Inmigratorias en la Argentina de Los 40.» *Publicar* 8 (7).
- Wallerstein Immanuel. 2010. «¿Guerra de divisas?, por supuesto». *La Jornada* [6/11/2010].
- Elías Norbert. 1982. *Sociología fundamental*. Barcelona. Gedisa.
- Wolf Eric. 1993. *Europa y la gente sin historia*. Buenos Aires. Fondo de Cultura Económica.
- Wolf Eric. 1999. «Cognizing ‘Cognized Models.’» *American Anthropologist*, New Series Vol. 101 (1): 19–22.
- Adler Judith. 1989. «Originis of the Sightseeing.» *Annals of Tourism Research* 16: 7–29.
- Latour Bruno. 2004. *Políticas da natureza como fazer ciencia na democracia*. Sao Paulo. EDUSC.
- Thévenot Laurent. *L'actonaupluriel. Sociologie des régimesd'engagement*. La Découverte. París.
- SOURCES
- AET.2009, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014, y 2015 (varios ejemplares). Anuario estadístico de turismo. Ministerio de Turismo de la Nación Argentina. En <http://desarrolloturistico.gob.ar/anuarios-estadisticos>.
- CAT. 2010. Cámara Argentina de Turismo. Informe económico cuatrimestral sobre la actividad de viajes y turismo. En <http://www.hmi-argentina.com/archivos/1288720848.pdf>
- MINTUR. 2015. Ministerio de Turismo de la Nación Argentina. En <http://www.turismo.gov.ar/>.
- SIET. 2015. Sistema de Información y Estadística Turística. Ministerio de Turismo de la Nación Argentina. En<http://siet.desarrolloturistico.gov.ar/>.
- UNWTO. 2015. *United Nations World Tourism Organization*. www.unwto.org
- WB. 2015. *World Bank*. www.data.worldbank.org
- CEPAL. 2015. *Estudio económico de América Latina y el Caribe*. Comisión Económica para América Latina y el Caribe. Enwww.cepal.org.